

The question of meaning as a path to transformation. Part 2: Useful tools

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Abstract

This article presents pedagogical tools for introducing the question of meaning to students in higher technical education. The author describes practical approaches aimed at helping technically oriented students reflect on their place and action in the world. Particular attention is given to two tools: the “See – Judge – Act” method, which encourages critical observation, ethical evaluation, and responsible action, and Aristotle’s theory of the four causes, which helps analyse reality by examining its origin, structure, process, and purpose. These tools are presented as accessible ways to develop practical intelligence, ethical awareness, and reflective engagement with reality. The article argues that such approaches can open a path toward deeper understanding and personal transformation by linking technical thinking with the search for meaning.

Keywords

question of meaning; See–Judge–Act; Aristotle’s four causes; ethics; pedagogy; human development; reflective practice; philosophy in technical education; philosophy of education

Introduction

For the record, in this text, I share the way in which, during my years of teaching students in higher technical education, I approached the question of meaning. In the first part of the article published previously (Urbain 2025), I presented how I formulated the question of meaning starting from an inspiring image that deeply marked me and continues to do so: a little figure coming out of an eggshell and scratching his head, wondering what is happening; the shell forming the dot of a question mark.

In this second part, I present tools used to pose this very question of meaning. My concern has always been to prioritise what could help students coming from horizons other than philosophy and theology, while remaining accessible to them. In this spirit, the aim was to meet students in their everyday lives and offer them that which would make sense within their daily life as technicians.

The challenge was to open students’ minds to questioning with tools they called ‘practical’, i.e., tools that enabled them to activate their practical intelligence. At the time, I favoured three

tools: ‘See – Judge – Act’, ‘Aristotle’s four causes’, and ‘The problem-solving method applied to the question of meaning’. Below, I explain how I used the first two tools in my teaching. The problem-solving method is more directly related to the engineering profession. Its framework is standardised and uses specific engineering tools that would take too long to present and explain here.

‘See – Judge – Act’

I have always posed the question of meaning from the perspective of who I am: ‘I am in the world, and I wonder how I fit into it.’ This explains why it is important for me to be aware of and knowledgeable about the environment in which I live and with which I interact. Modern environments are saturated with information from all directions: those who receive it are bombarded with it, receiving it in whole or in part, most often by zapping from one piece of information to another. There is intense pressure to guide consumers and focus their attention on what consumer society decides upstream, creating new needs rather than responding to what is necessary and, better still, essential. To remain free in such a context, it is necessary to identify what is at stake in order to choose and retain what has added value.

The ‘See – Judge – Act’ tool (Cardijn 1982, 88) allows this exercise to be carried out in a relevant and effective manner. Educate the eye to ‘see’ first, to identify realities that are not immediately obvious: be curious, take an interest in the simple things in everyday life as well as the more complex ones, pay attention to the small details that have been carefully crafted and shaped, and that make all the difference. The state of the world depends in part on the quality of my relationship with it: if I am sad, the world will appear grey to me; if, on the contrary, I am happy, the world will appear bright.

Furthermore, the way a person looks at things also determines the value. I remember a quote from Albert Jacquard (Jacquard 1983, 89) that I always recall from memory and that has had a profound impact on my personal and professional life: “We are what the gaze of others makes of us; when the gaze of others despises us, we become despicable, and when the gaze of others makes us wonderful, we are wonderful. What matters is to see ourselves as wonderful in the eyes of others.”

This means that the gaze is not simply a reception of information present in our environment, but that it reflects the intention of the person looking, which can be the best or the worst, contempt, harshness, or exclusion, or, on the contrary, esteem, empathy, and solidarity. The gaze cast upon people and things expresses the respect of the beholder or, on the contrary, is nothing but contempt and disdain. Seeing, like hearing, touching, smelling, and tasting, are the senses that allow us to perceive the realities that surround us, the here and now in which I live and exist.

After seeing comes ‘*judging*’ in the etymological sense of the term: ‘krinein’. This involves sorting through everything that the senses capture and bring to our attention, separating what is acceptable from what is less so: identifying what is at stake, evaluating, comparing, reasoning, and applying theories before validating what I keep and develop.

This is the moment of ethics. That of codes of conduct and that which goes beyond codes, which are certainly necessary points of support, but not sufficient; that which, on the contrary, leads each human being to discover themselves.

The first level of ethics organises the relationships of each human being with their surroundings in each of their living environments. Controllers ensure that the various precepts are respected and call people to order or condemn them when they overstep the mark.

The second level of ethics invites each human being to reconnect with their inner self by delving into their depths to bring to light what is still unconscious and transform what is in the shadows by bringing it into the light. This ethical movement, practised through an approach proposed by depth psychology, among others, allows human beings to unfold the dimensions of their being and align their body, heart, and brain.

I often refer to the alignment of the 3 Cs – in French: corps, cœur, cerveau – that is, body, heart, and brain, each dimension being integrated into the human being, with no one dimension taking precedence over the other two. This alignment, which must be constantly renewed and is never achieved once and for all, is for me the path to human freedom: going deep within oneself allows one to discover the strengths that lie within and to extract them in order to transform them into integrated forces of life, moving from the rough and unpolished to the refined and finely chiselled.

The judgement in question allows us to know things and people at their core by separating what weighs us down from what makes us flourish. It echoes Socrates' 'Know thyself'. What allows us to connect with human nature and promote freedom is, in my opinion, the liberation of the forces of death to allow the forces of life to unfold.

Finally, the attention turns to 'act'. Action is very important for technical students. Theories that are not linked to concrete reality are more difficult to grasp for them. I share their view that an unrealised concept is sterile.

I remember the joy of a colleague, a mathematics professor, who was ecstatic about the proof of a theorem, especially when he had found another way to prove it. I can equally understand the near jubilation of a researcher in fundamental research when faced with a discovery that allows them to understand a particular mechanism or behaviour of one element in relation to another. But these discoveries are destined to migrate from the fundamental to the applied. No one imagines a fundamental researcher preoccupied with framing their discovery and content to admire it every morning. The beauty of science is this movement from theory to practice and vice versa.

In our case, the stages of 'Seeing' and 'Judging' allow us to identify the essential characteristics of something that occurs and concerns us. The response can then be given with greater knowledge and be better adapted and more effective. I often use the expression 'ethics in action'.

Following the presentation of the 'See – Judge – Act' tool, I asked the students to explain how they would approach a broken engine as engineers. The radical solution was to dismantle the engine to see what needed to be fixed. In some cases, this was the most effective approach. But

in other cases, it was more appropriate to list everything that could be malfunctioning. A distinction was made between a combustion engine and an electric motor. As examples, citing what I remember for a combustion engine: a clogged fuel filter, a faulty fuel pump, dirty or blocked injectors, a blocked or punctured fuel line, and other technical delights... the reader will understand that I am not a technician. This other approach involves listing all the possible causes of the breakdown and seeing which one is responsible. This is the modern way of doing things in garages, when the technician connects the computer to the car to identify faults. This requires first constructing *a representation* of what is happening and what is at stake.

The 'See – Judge – Act' tool allows us to gather the constituent elements of a reality and select those that are useful for representing it. Representation is something that replaces reality, presenting it a second time, the first being reality itself. Gérard Fourez often used the example of a road map (Fourez 2003): the road map allows for the absence of the territory: it must be sufficient to plan a route and require no further information. It takes the place of the territory, it replaces it. Thus, territory is defined according to a particular point of view or in relation to a specific project: for example, that of a walker, motorist, geologist, soldier, wine lover, or something else entirely. Useful elements are selected. Maps of the same territory may vary depending on their intended use.

Going further into ways of understanding and knowing reality would go well beyond the scope of this article.

Aristotle's four causes

This tool allows us to answer the question of meaning as applied to any reality in the universe: where does it come from, where is it going, and how does it get there?

For a table, *the material cause* is the material from which the table is made; *the formal cause* is the idea of a table, the plan, the concept of its manufacturing process; *the efficient cause* is the manufacturing methods used to make the table; *the final cause* is who or what the table is made for (Aristote II, 3). For example, a rectangular wooden table made by hand with traditional tools as a gift from a little girl to her mother on Mother's Day.

The tool of the four causes also applies to human beings: *the material cause* for the dimensions of the human being (body, intelligence, affectivity, spirituality, imagination) and for the registers of their relationships (personal, interpersonal, natural, cultural, supernatural); *the formal cause* for the DNA code that determines human beings; *the efficient cause* for what makes human beings what they are, everything that shapes them, such as education, social, cultural, economic and political environment, training, people they meet, and experience gained; *the final cause* for what and why human beings live and lead their lives: on a humanistic level, everything they achieve by reaching their full potential, what they establish with others, what they build, leaving a mark of their passage on earth; on a spiritual level, their vocation in the fulfilment of their nature.

Conclusion

It is about a little figure coming out of his shell who appears to be questioning things, as suggested by the gesture of scratching his head. He emerges into a new environment that he will have to discover and become familiar with: one can imagine that he wonders where he is, what he should do, and how to go about it. Some things remain in the dark; not everything is clear.

Two tools have been made available to him so that he can look at and see what constitutes his new space, appreciate what it is, and act accordingly by understanding where it comes from, where it is heading, and how it moves from its origin to its end. It is within this framework that the tools “See – Judge – Act” and the “Four Causes of Aristotle” were presented.

In the next article, the aim will be to see how the little figure represents a point of view on the world and what this implies in terms of being an actor who gives meaning to what exists, on the one hand, and, on the other, how and in what way the question of meaning becomes an opportunity for the humanisation of the person that I am.

So, to be continued.

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